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**BOOK OF
ABSTRACTS**

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**21ST INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
ON NEAR INFRARED
SPECTROSCOPY**

GOOD VIBRATIONS, SMOOTH CONTOURS

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HYPERSPECTRAL IMAGING AS A HIGH-THROUGHPUT METHOD FOR MONITORING FUNGAL COLONIZATION ON BUILDING MATERIALS

Karen Butina-Ogorelec^{1,2}, Ana Gubenšek^{1,2,3}, Jakub Sandak^{1,2}, Faksawat Poohphajai^{1,2,4}, **Anna Sandak**^{1,2}

¹InnoRenew CoE, Izola, Slovenia, ²University of Primorska, Koper, Slovenia, ³University of Ljubljana, Ljubljana, Slovenia, ⁴Aalto University, Aalto, Finland

Materials exposed outdoors are prone to various deterioration processes. Architectural coatings are designed to protect surfaces against environmental and biotic degradation and/or to provide a decorative layer. Common surface treatments often include mineral oil binders and other ingredients that are known to have negative impacts on the environment. The use of toxic substances is increasingly restricted by legal regulations due to awareness of their negative environmental impacts. An alternative bioinspired concept for materials protection based on fungal biofilm is recently investigated in the ARCHI-SKIN project. In the first phase the morphological, functional, and social interactions in fungal communities naturally appearing on building materials are deeply investigated. The assessment of a variety of fungi that can thrive on exposed surfaces and understanding their interactions with various building materials is crucial to identify fungal species with a protective potential.

A set of 34 wood-based cladding materials were exposed and monitored in outdoor conditions. Hyperspectral imaging (HI) as a high-throughput method was used to understand the effect of fungal growth on material properties as well as to objectively quantify the infested area. Hyperspectral images were acquired with the FX17 camera (Specim, Finland) and LumoScanner program (Middleton Spectral Vision, Wisconsin). Data were analysed using Evince (Prediktera, Sweden). Spectral data were pre-processed using SNV before PCA. The loadings of the first principal components were plotted using Prism 9 (GraphPad Software, Massachusetts).

Simultaneously to hyperspectral imaging microbial growth was evaluated by wet swab technique and molecular identification of prevalent species. The surfaces were sampled using the wet swab and plated on DG-18 agar, which prevents the growth of bacteria and limits the growth of fast-growing fungi. Pure cultures were then isolated and identified through PCR amplification and Sanger sequencing of specific DNA regions/genes. Multi-sensor and multi-scale measurements were performed to assess the influence of surface properties (wettability and roughness) and material structure on fungal growth, species variability, and dominance. Proposed techniques enabled the identification of features that promote/inhibit fungal colonization and revealed the preference of certain fungi for specific materials. Both the material type and the climate condition at the exposure site influence fungal colonization and the variability of microorganisms. The samples in close spatial proximity exhibited different fungal microbiota, demonstrating that fungal colonization across samples is not random. This study is a starting point for more exhaustive assays that aim to develop novel solutions for materials protection based on controlled and optimized fungal biofilm formation.